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THE BALANCE BETWEEN SPIRITUALITY AND GLOBAL VALUES: A PHILOSOPHICAL APPROACH

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Abstract: This article examines the relationship between globalization and individuality, with a special focus on the formation of an individual's moral self-awareness. In the context of rapidly growing global integration, cultural exchange, and information flow, the individual is exposed to diverse value systems that significantly influence identity formation. The study analyzes how globalization shapes personal consciousness, behavior, and moral choices, while also highlighting the importance of preserving inner individuality and cultural identity. It is argued that moral self-awareness emerges as a key mechanism that helps individuals balance global influences with personal and cultural values, ensuring psychological stability and ethical consistency in modern society.

Keywords: globalization, individuality, moral self-awareness, identity formation, cultural values, personal development, ethical consciousness, social transformation

The 21st century is characterized by the acceleration of globalization processes. As a result of the development of information technologies, transport and communication means, the world is becoming a "single information space". This situation has a strong impact on all areas of human life, in particular, on the spiritual world of a person and the process of self-realization.

In the conditions of globalization, a person develops in two directions at the same time: on the one hand, he accepts global culture and universal values; on the other hand, it tries to preserve its national and individual characteristics. From this point of view, the issue of individuality and spiritual self-realization is of urgent importance.

The concept of globalization and its essence

Globalization is a process of strengthening and deepening of economic, political, cultural and informational relations between the countries of the world. It affects all areas of human activity.

The main features of globalization:

acceleration of information flow; strengthening of cultural ties; economic integration; development of communication tools.

However, there are also negative aspects of globalization, which include cultural homogenization, weakening of national values, and weakening of personal identity.

Individuality and individual spirituality

Individuality is a unique way of thinking, feelings, views and life position of each person. Spirituality is a complex socio-psychological phenomenon related to the inner world, values and moral principles of a person.

A person's spiritual self-awareness is manifested in the following aspects:

understand their own values;

setting life goals;

making independent decisions in moral choices;

to know their national and cultural roots.

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Maintaining individuality in a global environment is an important factor for the internal stability of a person.

Problems of spiritual self-realization in the context of globalization

The process of globalization brings many opportunities to the individual as well as a number of challenges. The most important of them is the danger of loss of spiritual identity.

Main problems:

distraction of the mind through information pressure;

weakening of national values under the influence of popular culture;

decrease in independence of personal opinion;

the rise of consumer culture.

These situations make the process of self-realization difficult.

Factors ensuring moral stability

A person's spiritual stability and self-awareness depends on the following factors:

Family education is the environment in which the first values of a person are formed.

The educational system develops critical thinking and spiritual outlook.

National culture forms the identity of a person.

Religious and moral values provide internal stability.

Information culture - forms the ability to choose the right information.

A balance between globalization and individuality

Although there is a conflict between globalization and individualism, they can coexist. While globalization creates wide opportunities for man, individuality defines his spiritual limit.

Participating in global processes while preserving individuality ensures the full development of a person. Critical thinking and spiritual independence are important in this process. Also, globalization is not only an external socio-economic process, but also a complex phenomenon that directly affects the inner spiritual world of a person. Today, a person is forced to find his place among different cultural models, information flows and ideological influences. This, in turn, makes the process of spiritual self-realization of a person more relevant and complex.

The preservation of human identity in the global cultural environment depends on his inner spiritual stability. If a person does not realize his values, national identity and moral principles, he can lose his individuality under external influences.

Therefore, in the conditions of globalization, the spiritual self-awareness of the individual is considered as a matter of not only philosophical, but also socio-pedagogical importance.

Today, in scientific research, special attention is paid to the issues of self-awareness of the individual, the problem of identity, and spiritual stability. This creates the need for a deeper study of the relationship between globalization and individuality.

In traditional philosophical and sociological studies, globalization is interpreted as a "multifactorial process" that affects the structural changes in human consciousness and personality. This process reshapes not only economic or political relations, but also a person's worldview, value system, and spiritual identity. In particular, as a result of the widespread use of digital technologies, a person is becoming an "information person." In this case, a person begins to make his life decisions not only based on personal experience, but also on influences in the global information field. As a result, the share of external influences in the process of spiritual self-realization increases, and the issue of maintaining internal independence becomes even more important. Today, scientists are putting forward the concept of a balance between "global personality" and "local identity." According to this approach, a modern person can be formed as both a global citizen and a representative of national culture at the same time. This requires a person to have a high level of moral stability, critical thinking and self-awareness. From this point

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of view, spiritual self-awareness is not only an internal psychological process, but also an important factor determining a person's position in the social environment.

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